

Using multi-plane light conversion for 2D, direct laser interference patterning

SABRINA HAMMOUTI,¹ DMITRY NUZHIN,² IVAN GUSACHENKO,²
GWENN PALLIER,² GUILLAUME LABROILLE,² AURÉLIEN SIKORA,¹
MARC FAUCON,¹ AND GIROLAMO MINCUZZI^{1,*}

¹ALPhANOV, Aquitania Institute of Optics, Rue F. Mitterrand, 33400 Talence, France

²CAILABS, 1 Rue Nicolas Joseph Cugnot, 35000 Rennes, France

*girolamo.mincuzzi@alphanov.com

Abstract: We introduced and tested what we believe to be a novel approach for surface texturing via direct laser interference patterning (DLIP). This new setup integrates a module implementing multi-plane light conversion (MPLC) technology. The module has been specifically engineered to directly generate a matrix of 2×2 identical sub-beams from a single incoming beam. Differently from a conventional DLIP set-up, no diffractive element or multi-facets prism has been used, with the critical advantage to prevent misalignment issues, temporal overlap mismatch and phase front aberrations. Utilizing a 350-fs laser, we achieved a 2D interference pattern with a contrast as high as 85%. The system incorporates a pulse-on-demand (POD) feature and a fast galvo scanner, enabling the generation on the fly of high aspect ratio, regular structures at scan speeds as high as 10 m/s. Moreover, we explored the potential of integrating this setup into a roll-to-roll pilot line, which allows for the continuous texturing of large surfaces. This integration is crucial to adopt the technology for industrial applications, as it facilitates high-throughput processing over large areas. We believe our results not only prove the feasibility and the advantages of using DLIP with MPLC for precise and high-contrast surface texturing but also point-out its utility for industrial-scale applications, paving the way for more efficient and scalable production processes in material surface engineering.

© 2024 Optica Publishing Group under the terms of the [Optica Open Access Publishing Agreement](#)

1. Introduction

Use of ultrashort pulse lasers (UPL) for texturing the surface of materials has been shown to be the right choice when targeting structures with sizes ranging from submicron to tens of microns, with high precision and accuracy [1–5]. Furthermore, the availability in the last decade of reliable, industrial, kW class, UPL sources emitting MHz pulses with duration comprised between some hundreds of fs and few ps, and maximum pulse energy E exceeding 1 mJ, has enabled the texturing of large surfaces with increasing throughput. This advancement enhances the readiness of this technological approach, making it primed for industrial exploitation [6–8].

This is particularly true when considering metallic surfaces, where a variety of different texturing techniques and surface structure morphologies has been shown. For instance, in Laser Induced Periodic Surface Structuring (LIPSS), 1D, nanometric ripples are obtained after the interaction of Surface Plasmon Polariton (SPP) with forthcoming photons [9–11]. Periodical, 2D structures can be obtained by controlling the delay between two successive pulses and the relative polarisation orientation [12]. Laser Direct Writing (LDW) of metallic surfaces is a subtractive texturing approach based on laser ablation. In this case it is possible to generate structures of hundreds or tens of microns with a minimum size comparable to the beam size [13]. To overcome this limitation, DLIP technique can be used. DLIP consists in superposing coherently two or more beams tilted by angle θ with the result to obtain an interference pattern. Use of DLIP has been reported for different kind of periodic surface modification including oxidation pattern

or generation of micro-structures pattern [15]. In the last case, maxima will ablate more than the minima with the result to generate micrometric or submicrometric structures smaller than the beam size [10,14]. The higher the contrast the higher the structures aspect ratio which is a specific requirement for some applications with high market impact like the generation of superhydrophobic, anti-icing or anti-reflection surfaces, as well as the increase of the surface to area ratio to improve the adhesion of two stacked layers [4]. Several factors have a bearing on the interference contrast. We mention in particular the relative direction of polarisation, phase front aberrations and the spatial and temporal coherence of the superposing beams [16]. The last could be a limiting factor when the pulse duration becomes as short as some hundreds of fs [17]. In a conventional DLIP set-up, the beam is split in a set of sub-beams by a diffractive optical element (DOE) which are then parallelised by a prism and superposed by a lens [17,18]. Although this experimental approach is quite simple and effective, it shows some drawbacks when considering the superposition of more than 2 beams. In fact, the fabrication of multi-faces prisms with the right surface planarity and the right apex represents a challenge limiting the possibility to obtain parallel beams. Moreover, diffractive components induce chromatic aberrations which can negatively impact the pattern contrast. This is particularly true when considering femtosecond laser sources with relatively large emission band.

Further set-ups have been proposed replacing prisms by mirrors. Nevertheless, their optical and mechanical integration with optical systems delivering the beam with high-speed scanners, both galvanometric and polygon, may show some challenges [5,19].

Here for the first time a novel DLIP experimental approach is introduced and tested. In our set-up a single beam is split in a matrix of 2×2 sub beams by means of a module specifically designed and engineered for the present study and based on MPLC [20,21]. The beams matrix was therefore imaged through a 4f-4f optical system onto an f-theta lens, being previously reflected by a couple of a galvo mirrors. The superposition of the 2×2 beams leads to a pattern made of 5×5 maxima. Being our MPLC module implementation based on reflection over optical elements (see MPLC description reported in paragraph 3), chromatic aberrations are minimized and all the beams outgoing the MPLC module have the same polarisation than the incoming one. In addition, differently from the case of prisms, the set of sub beams have similar optical path with the consequence to optimise the interference contrast. Relative misalignment of the beams is prevented since any prism is used. After a characterisation of the interference pattern, the potential and the effectiveness of this set-up has been extensively explored in micromachining tests of stainless-steel samples. The aspect ratio of the structures has been maximised passing from a single pass to a multi-passes approach. The last was made possible thanks to the use of a POD feature enabling the delivering of each pulse with a spatial accuracy $< 1 \mu\text{m}$. Finally, our set-up has been integrated in a roll-to-roll line showing the potential for a continuous 2D - DLIP texturing over surfaces as large as $\sim \text{m}^2$. In conclusion, the aim of the present study is to show the advantages, and the potential introduced by our novel set-up in texturing metallic surfaces via DLIP technique.

2. Experimental

We utilised a $\lambda = 1030 \text{ nm}$, pulse duration $\tau = 350 \text{ fs}$ laser sources (Tangor by Amplitude). The laser can emit a maximum average power $P = 100 \text{ W}$ with a maximum repetition rate $f = 10 \text{ MHz}$. The beam delivered by the source was injected in a beam reducer ($0.5\times$) to fit with the entrance of a MPLC module. The module is a Canunda provided by Cailabs. It has been specifically designed, engineered and fabricated to split an ingoing beam in 4 identical outgoing sub-beams. The module used in this work provides a fixed splitting pattern, for it is completely passive, has no moving mechanical or electronically addressed parts. The transmission of the module was measured to be 80%. A lens with focal length $L_4 = 1000 \text{ mm}$ was placed right at the exit of the module to compensate the divergence of the 4 beams and make them parallels. The MPLC

technology makes alternatively possible to directly generate 4 parallel beams without the use of the lens.

The 4 parallel beams were successively injected in a Galvo Scanner having an entrance of 20 mm (Excelliscan 20 by Scanlab) and superposed by a telecentric, f -theta lens of 100 mm, resulting in a matrix of 5×5 beams. The beam was firstly full characterised by means of a beam profiler (WinCamD from DataRay with a pixel of $4 \mu\text{m}$, and μEye by EDS with a pixel of $1.6 \mu\text{m}$) with the acquisition of intensity profiles in different points all along its propagation from the laser source to the focus. We carried out three sets of tests (i), (ii) and (iii). In set (i) we fixed $E = 50 \mu\text{J}$ and patterned a fixed, 1 mm thick, $5 \text{ cm} \times 5 \text{ cm}$ stainless steel polished substrate. The patterning was made using the approach on the fly both with a single scan, and with multiple scans N ($N = 5$ and $N = 30$). The scan speed v and f were adjusted to fix the distance between two successive pulses d (see Fig. 2(a)) equal to the distance s between two adjacent columns of the 5×5 beams pattern $s = d = 14 \mu\text{m}$. The same distance was fixed between two scanning lines $h = s = d = 14 \mu\text{m}$ (see Fig. 2(b)). Not POD features were used.

To enhance the aspect ratio ρ of the structures, in set (ii) we followed two distinct approaches. On one side, the surface was patterned using a “drilling” approach, which involved delivering N pulses (N was fixed equal to 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 100 and 500) at each point before repeating the process at the adjacent point. On the other side, we adopted an approach on the fly with multiple scans (N). Differently from set (i) pulses emission and scanner movements were synchronized using a “pulse-on-demand” approach, as described elsewhere [22]. We used the same, fixed, stainless-steel sample than set (i) as well as the condition $h = s = d = 14 \mu\text{m}$. We fixed $N = 10, 30, 50$ and 100. Finally in set (iii) we patterned a $200 \mu\text{m}$ thick stainless-steel coil which was conveyed through a roll-to-roll line and moved with a line speed v_1 (see Fig. 1). In this case the beam was scanned only in the direction perpendicular to v_1 . In the direction of the scan speed, we fixed $h = s = d = 14 \mu\text{m}$ whilst v_1 was adjusted to have $h = 5 s$ being s the distance between the last row of the Line 1 and the first row of Line 2 (see Fig. 2(c)). All the results were characterized through a profilometer (Zeiss, Smart Proof 5), an optical microscope (Mitutoyo MFB) and a SEM (Tescan, Vega 3 SBU).

Fig. 1. The figure depicts a schematic view of the set-up used during the experimental study.

Fig. 2. The figure schematises the relative positioning of 5×5 sub-beams matrixes correspondent to two successive pulses in two adjacent scanning lines for different cases. To avoid any misunderstanding all the pulses and the correspondent sub-pulses matrix have been highlighted with a different colour. Figure 2(a) is relative to a generic case when the distance between the centres of the two pulses in a line is d and the distance between the two pulses in two successive lines is h . Figure 2(b) is relative to the case of $h = d = s$ being the last the distance between two sub-pulses of the same matrix. Finally, Fig. 2(c) shows the case of $d = s$ and $h = 5s$.

3. MPLC and beam characterisation

Multi-plane light conversion (MPLC) is a beam shaping technology based on the use of a set of phase plates (PPs) [20,21,23]. In a reflective implementation of a MPLC module, an incoming beam is reflected on the surface of a multiplicity of PPs which have been specifically designed to yield an outgoing beam with a wanted beam shape. In the design of each PP it is important to precisely calculate the propagation of the beam after each reflection [23,24]. Interestingly, this technology makes possible an intricate control and fine tailoring of both the beam's intensity and phase profile and the outgoing profile is kept substantially unchanged along a relatively long propagation distance [25,26]. The last enables a depth of field and a working field which are larger than other commercially available technologies [26,27]. This is crucial when the laser beam is scanned through an f-theta lens for laser machining purposes [28,29]. Finally, MPLC keep unchanged both the beam polarization, spectrum, and pulse duration, making this beam shaping technology one of the most promising when coupled with femtosecond lasers. In Fig. 3 is reported the spatial distribution of the electromagnetic field intensity $I(x,y)$ relative to different positions along its propagation direction. Starting from the exit of the laser sources (see Figure 3(a)) the beam observes a symmetric Gaussian distribution ($M^2 < 1.3$) with a beam size ($1/e^2$ of the peak) of $2\omega_0 \approx 3.2$ mm. Figure 3(b) shows the $I(x,y)$ of the beam after the size reduction required to fit with the entrance of the MPLC module. In this case, we estimated $2\omega_0 \approx 1.6$ mm. Finally, Fig. 3(c) shows $I(x,y)$ at the exit of the MPLC module.

It can be observed (see Fig. 3(c)) that the four generated sub-beams observe a quite similar $I(x,y)$ distribution, with a symmetric Gaussian profile and an average beam size which has been estimated to be 1.6 mm. The maximum distance d between the pulses (diagonal of the matrix) has been evaluated to be ≈ 10 mm.

In Fig. 4 (left) is shown the measured interference pattern generated by the superposition of the 4 beams by means of a telecentric lens $f = 100$ mm. It consists of a 2D, 5×5 maxima, pattern. The FWHM of each peak is nearly $10 \mu\text{m}$ whilst we evaluated the DLIP period as peak-to-peak distance $s \approx 14 \mu\text{m}$. The overall FWHM of the whole pattern is $l \approx 70 \mu\text{m}$. We observe that the DLIP period s can be calculated from the general formula in case of 4 superposing beams [4]

$$s = \frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \theta} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3. The figure shows the beam intensity profile in correspondence of three different planes perpendicular to the beam propagation direction: (a) is just before the beam reducer, (b) just before the entrance to the MPLC module and (c) at the exit of the MPLC module.

where θ is the inclination angle of the beams respect to the f -theta optical axes, i.e.

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{d}{2w_d}\right) \quad (2)$$

with $w_d = 125$ mm the working distance of the f -theta lens and $d \approx 10$ mm the diagonal distance between the superposing beams at the lens (see Fig. 3(c)). It can be extracted $s \approx 13$ μm which is compatible with the value we measured experimentally. It follows that one can expect a maximum number of sub-beams in the focus which is $1/s = 70/13 \approx 5$.

Fig. 4. (left) 2D (X and Y) beam intensity profile on the superposition plane of the 2×2 sub-beams matrix measured by CCD camera (μEye by EDS). In the centre is reported the intensity profile along the Y direction and in the right the profile along the X direction.

Interestingly, for each peak we calculated the value of the contrast according to the following definition:

$$S = \frac{I_{max} - I_{min}}{I_{max} + I_{min}} \quad (3)$$

and then we obtained an average value of $S_{ave} = 82 \pm 3\%$. This value is $> 1/e^2$ ($= 67\%$) and can be considered as an indication that in our set-up, the use of femtosecond laser with a relatively low coherence length will have negligible impact on the aspect ratio of the pattern features. We highlight that from a theoretical point of view MPLC technology can generate features as small as the wavelength although the engineering of the optical set-up required to transport the beam outgoing the module will be extremely challenging (size of the apertures, stringent requirements on the optical surfaces, etc.). A further and more practical possibility relies on the use of our set-up but with an f -theta lens with smaller focal length.

4. Patterning of stainless steel: results and discussion

4.1. Single scan patterning

Figure 5(a) shows the surface of stainless steel after a single scan line ($N = 1$ “on the fly”). In this case v and f were adjusted to have $s = d = 14 \mu\text{m}$. A regular pattern of 2D structures is clearly visible. This is confirmed by the measurement of the profile along the scanning direction (see Fig. 5(b)) showing a clearly periodic pattern. We highlight that the whole acquisition length of the profilometer was $d_{\text{tot}} = 548.5 \mu\text{m}$ which has been reduced to $400 \mu\text{m}$ in Fig. 5(b) for graphical limitations. The FFT analysis was calculated taking into account d_{tot} (see Fig. 5(c)) and shows a peak in correspondence of the Wavelength Number $\# = 39$ which, according to the FFT sampling executed by the profilometer software (Zeiss Confomap) corresponds to a pitch of $p_p = d_{\text{tot}} / (\#) = 548.5/39 \approx 14 \mu\text{m}$. This value is consistent with the s distance observed in Fig. 4. From Fig. 5(b) we can evaluate the peak-to-valley of the pattern obtained after a single scan to be roughly $p_v = 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ leading to an aspect ratio $\rho = p_v/p_p \approx 0.04$. Increasing ρ would bring about the possibility to boost some surface functionalities like wettability, light trapping, surface adhesion. To this end, on the fly multiple scans (N) are required. Figure 5(d) shows the case where $N = 30$. We observe that although the pattern remains regular in the direction perpendicular to the scan direction (i.e. red row), this is not the case along the scan direction (i.e. yellow row). In fact, scan after scan, at a given position along the scan direction, pulses may be delivered with an accuracy that is not as high as required to maintain a regular pattern. We observe that the positioning error relative to each pulse is $\Delta a \leq (v/f)$. Being $v = 1.4 \text{ m/s}$ and $f = 200 \text{ kHz}$, is $\Delta a \leq 7 \mu\text{m}$ which is half of the s value. Increasing N induces continuous ablation of material in the scanning direction, accounting for the morphology observed in Fig. 5(d) which is relative to $N = 30$.

Fig. 5. Figure 5(a) shows the optical micrograph of the surface after 1 pass following an approach “on the fly”. Figure 5(b) shows the profile of the same surface than in Fig. 5(a) and in Fig. 5(c) is reported its FFT. We observe that the last has been extracted considering the whole profile acquisition length which was $548.5 \mu\text{m}$. Figure 5(d) shows the SEM micrograph of the patterned surface after $N = 30$ passes.

4.2. Multi-scan patterning

To maintain a 2D patterning while increasing N and therefore ρ , two distinct approaches were followed and compared. On one side, the surface was patterned using a “drilling” approach, with N pulses. As mentioned in the experimental section it consists in delivering a pulse and the associated 5×5 sub-pulses pattern in the same point of the surface N times before repeat the process in an adjacent point spaced by $d = 5s = 70 \mu\text{m}$ (see Fig. 2(a)). On the other side, pulses were delivered on the fly with a fixed scan speed and by scanning the surface N times. In this case it is important to deliver each pulse with high accuracy and high scan to scan repeatability. To this end pulses emission and mirrors movement were synchronized using a POD approach where the pulse emission is triggered by the scanner. In our set-up the scanner can take into account the mirrors acceleration and trigger the pulse emission with accuracy and scan-to-scan repeatability $\leq 1 \mu\text{m}$ as already reported in [22].

Figure 7 shows SEM micrographs of the stainless-steel surface patterned following a drilling approach for $N = 10$, $N = 50$, $N = 100$, $N = 500$ (respectively (a), (b), (c) and (d)). In all cases, a 2D patterning with a pitch of nearly $14 \mu\text{m}$ is obtained. We highlight that this can be interpreted as

Fig. 6. Measurement of the profile of the structures along two scanning directions reported as X (Top) and along the direction Y perpendicular to X (Bottom)

Fig. 7. SEM micrograph of the surface after $N = 10$ (a), $N = 50$ (b), $N = 100$ (c) and $N = 500$ (d). Micrographs on top row are relative to a lower magnification than the row on the bottom

Fig. 8. SEM micrographs of the surface textured on the fly with a POD synchronisation with $N = 10$ scans (left) and $N = 100$ scans (right). The scan speed v was fixed to 5 m/s (top) and 10 m/s (bottom)

evidence that the pointing of the pattern coming out of the MPLC module is stable. Passing from $N = 10$ to $N = 100$ the pattern becomes more regular and the structures well defined. In Fig. 6 are plotted the profile along the X direction (Top) and the Y direction (bottom) when is $N = 100$. A ρ value approaching 0.5 can be extracted. When increasing N to 500, it becomes apparent that the homogeneity of the structures morphology decreases as well as the ρ value (see Fig. 6(d)). Very likely the ablation rate in correspondence of the pattern valleys approaches zero due to the tapering and saturation phenomena in general whilst it is not negligible in correspondence of the top with the consequence to reduce the ρ value [30]. It can be observed that the time required to switch on and switch off the laser when passing from one point to the successive one has a huge bearing on the t_p value [31,22]. Utilizing techniques that enable effective synchronization between the pulse emission and positioning makes it possible to adopt an approach on the fly while maintaining precise pulse placement accuracy, surpassing the peak-to-peak distance. This capability enables the retention of 2D patterning for a large number of repetitions ($N \gg 1$) and relatively high scan speed values in the range of several meters per second. Patterning tests were carried out fixing both $E = 50 \mu\text{J}$ and pulse-to-pulse distance $d = v / f = 14 \mu\text{m}$. The last was achieved for different couples (v, f) i.e. $v = 5, 7, 10 \text{ m/s}$ and $f = 3.6 \text{ MHz}, 5 \text{ MHz}, 7.2 \text{ MHz}$. Finally the number of scans was fixed to $N = 90, 95$ and 100. Figure 8 shows the case of $N = 10$ (left) and $N = 100$ (right) for $v = 5 \text{ m/s}$ (top) and $v = 10 \text{ m/s}$ (bottom). When is $v = 5 \text{ m/s}$ and $N = 100$ (see in-set of Fig. 8), structures are very regular and well defined.

When is $v = 10 \text{ m/s}$ and $N = 100$, we evaluated $t_p \approx 5 \text{ min/cm}^2$ and $\rho > 0.5$, whilst in the case of $N = 100$ drilling we extracted $t_p \approx 12.5 \text{ min/cm}^2$. Similarly to the drilling case, the pulse energy was $E = 50 \mu\text{J}$ and the average power $P \approx 35 \text{ W}$ meaning that further reduction of t_p can be reached by increasing P via the repetition rate and increasing proportionally v [32].

5. Continuous, roll to roll patterning

The possibility to extend the patterning over large area with a continuous process can open the possibility to address at industrial scale interesting applications like production of large surfaces showing anti-icing properties for aeronautics industry, texturing of electrodes for energy

storage application, etc. [4,5] To this end, we integrated our set-up in a roll-to-roll pilot line (see Fig. 1) already described in a previous paper, with the aim to continuously pattern a coil of stainless-steel thick $200\ \mu\text{m}$ [8]. Figure 9(a) shows an overview of the set-up. The in-set of Fig. 9(b) shows a detail of the patterned part (yellowish stripe). Both v and v_1 were adjusted to obtain a homogeneous patterning fulfilling the condition depicted in Fig. 2(c). Figure 9(c) shows the SEM micrograph of the surface obtained when $v = 7\ \text{m/s}$ and $v_1 = 3\ \text{mm/s}$ after a single scan ($N = 1$). As it can be observed the patterning is highly regular and structures equally spaced. The scanning field has been evaluated to be $40\ \text{mm}$, which is quite compatible with the specification value of the f-theta lens i.e. $50\ \text{mm}$. An improvement can be obtained by positioning more precisely the f-theta lens respect to its entrance pupil. We highlight that the performances of the encoders driving the coils of our line limits the accuracy in the positioning of the coil to roughly $100\ \mu\text{m}$. Although this prevented the possibility to increase the ρ value by a multi-scanning approach, the results clearly show the potential of our technological approach to continuously process large surfaces.

Fig. 9. In Fig. 9(a) is shown a part of the roll-to-roll set-up with the galvo scanner (grey box) and beneath the mirror-like stainless-steel coil. In Fig. 9(b) is reported a particular of the same set-up, including the textured part of the coil which corresponds to the yellowish-iridescent stripe positioned in the middle of the same coil. In Fig. 9(c) is reported a SEM micrograph of the surface after $N = 1$ pass.

6. Conclusion

We introduced and tested a novel approach to surface texturing by means of DLIP technique. A new set-up has been utilized based on the effective integration of a module implementing the MPLC technology. The module has been specifically engineered to generate a matrix of 2×2 outgoing, identical sub beams from a single ingoing beam. A 2D pattern has been generated with a $350\ \text{fs}$ beam and showing a contrast as high as 85% . Use of a POD and a fast, galvo-scanner makes it possible to generate, at scan speed values as high as $10\ \text{m/s}$, 2D patterns made of high aspect ratio regular structures. Interestingly, we have shown and tested the possibility to integrate the set-up in a roll-to-roll pilot line which enables the continuous texturing of large surfaces, making this approach primed for application in industrial environment.

Funding. HORIZON EUROPE Framework Programme (862100, NewSkin).

Acknowledgements. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862100 (NewSkin). The output reflects the views only of the author(s), and the European Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Disclosures. The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data availability. Data underlying the results presented in this paper are not publicly available at this time but may be obtained from the authors upon reasonable request

References

1. A. Y. Vorobyev and C. Guo, "Direct femtosecond laser surface nano/microstructuring and its applications," *Laser Photonics Rev.* **7**(3), 385–407 (2013).
2. F. Fraggelakis, G. Mincuzzi, J. Lopez, *et al.*, "Texturing metal surface with MHz ultra-short laser pulses," *Opt. Express* **25**(15), 18131–18139 (2017).
3. A. Sikora, S. Nourry, M. Faucon, *et al.*, "Role of the intensity profile in femtosecond laser surface texturing: An experimental study," *Appl. Surface Sci. Adv.* **6**, 100136 (2021).
4. A. F. Lasagni, C. Gachot, K. E. Trinh, *et al.*, "Direct laser interference patterning, 20 years of development: from the basics to industrial applications," *Proc. SPIE* **10092**, 1009211 (2017).
5. L. Mulko, M. Soldera, and A. F. Lasagni, "Structuring and functionalization of non-metallic materials using direct laser interference patterning: a review," *Nanophotonics* **11**(2), 203–240 (2022).
6. F. Ränke, R. Baumann, B. Voisiat, *et al.*, "High throughput laser surface micro-structuring of polystyrene by combining direct laser interference patterning with polygon scanner technology," *Materials Lett. X* **14**, 100144 (2022).
7. G. Mincuzzi, A. Bourtereau, L. Gemini, *et al.*, "Through the Forming Process of Femtosecond-Laser Nanotextured Sheets for Production of Complex 3D Parts," *Appl. Sci.* **13**(22), 12500 (2023).
8. G. Račiukaitis, "Ultra-Short Pulse Lasers for Microfabrication: A Review," *IEEE J. Select. Topics Quantum Electron.* **27**(6), 1–12 (2021).
9. G. D. Tsibidis, C. Fotakis, and E. Stratakis, "From ripples to spikes: A hydrodynamical mechanism to interpret femtosecond laser-induced self-assembled structures," *Phys. Rev. B* **92**(4), 041405 (2015).
10. A. Sikora, M. Faucon, L. Gemini, *et al.*, "LIPSS and DLIP: From hierarchical to mutually interacting, homogeneous, structuring," *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **591**, 153230 (2022).
11. F. Fraggelakis, G. D. Tsibidis, and E. Stratakis, "Ultrashort pulsed laser induced complex surface structures generated by tailoring the melt hydrodynamics," *Opto-Electron. Adv.* **5**(3), 210052 (2022).
12. F. Fraggelakis, G. Mincuzzi, J. Lopez, *et al.*, "Controlling 2D laser nano structuring over large area with double femtosecond pulses," *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **470**, 677–686 (2019).
13. C. Gaudiuso, A. Volpe, F. P. Mezzapesa, *et al.*, "Tailoring the Coefficient of Friction by Direct Laser Writing Surface Texturing," *Micromachines* **15**(1), 7 (2023).
14. A. Sikora, M. Faucon, G. Mincuzzi, *et al.*, "Fabrication of multisymmetrical hierarchical structures by direct laser interference patterning with 2 beams," *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **638**, 158086 (2023).
15. V. P. Veiko, R. A. Zakoldaev, E. A. Shakhno, *et al.*, "Thermochemical writing with high spatial resolution on Ti films utilising picosecond laser," *Opt. Mater. Express* **9**(6), 2729–2737 (2019).
16. S. R. J. Brueck, "Optical and Interferometric Lithography - Nanotechnology Enablers," *Proc. IEEE* **93**(10), 1704–1721 (2005).
17. Y. Nakata, "Interference Laser Processing," *Adv. Opt. Technol.* **5**(1), 29–38 (2016).
18. M. Bieda, M. Siebold, and A. F. Lasagni, "Fabrication of Sub-Micron Surface Structures on Copper, Stainless Steel and Titanium Using Picosecond Laser Interference Patterning," *Appl. Surf. Sci.* **387**, 175–182 (2016).
19. A. Peter, A. H. A. Lutey, S. Faas, *et al.*, "Direct laser interference patterning of stainless steel by ultrashort pulses for antibacterial surfaces," *Opt. Laser Technol.* **123**, 105954 (2020).
20. J. F. Morizur, L. Nicholls, P. Jian, *et al.*, "Programmable unitary spatial mode manipulation," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* **27**(11), 2524–2531 (2010).
21. P. Boucher, A. Goetschy, G. Sorelli, *et al.*, "Full characterization of the transmission properties of a multi-plane light converter," *Phys. Rev. Res.* **3**(2), 023226 (2021).
22. G. Mincuzzi, E. Audouard, A. Bourtereau, *et al.*, "Pulse to pulse control for highly precise and efficient micromachining with femtosecond lasers," *Opt. Express* **28**(12), 17209–17218 (2020).
23. J. F. Morizur, G. Labroille, and N. Treps, "Device for processing light/optical radiation, method and system for designing such a device," US Patent No. 10,324,286 (2016).
24. N. K. Fontaine, R. Ryf, H. Chen, *et al.*, "Laguerre-Gaussian mode sorter," *Nat. Commun.* **10**(1), 1865 (2019).
25. G. Pallier and J.-F. Poisson, "Beam shaping to scale up micro processing," *Photonics Views* **20**(1), 32–35 (2023).
26. I. Gusachenko, D. Nuzhdin, M. Ziat, *et al.*, "Tackling micro-processing challenges with beam shaping," *Proc. SPIE* **PC12873**, PC1287303 (2024).

27. C. Jacquard, G. Mincuzzi, M. Faucon, *et al.*, “Square top-hat and round top-hat laser beam shaping with multi-plane light conversion for femtosecond laser material microprocessing (Conference Presentation),” *Proc. SPIE* **11266**, 1126610 (2020).
28. G. Pallier, M. Dijoux, I. Gusachenko, *et al.*, “Versatile fully reflective beam splitter for high throughput manufacturing with high power green femtosecond laser,” *Proc. SPIE* **PC11988**, PC119880D (2022).
29. <https://www.cailabs.com/industrial-laser-processing/micro-processing/surface-processing/> Retrieved in data 31/07/2024.
30. J. Lopez, K. Mishchik, G. Mincuzzi, *et al.*, “Efficient Metal Processing Using High Average Power Ultrafast Laser,” *JLMN-J. Laser Micro/Nanoeng.* **12**(3), 1 (2017).
31. J. J. Kočica, J. Mur, J. Didierjean, *et al.*, “Pulse-on-Demand Operation for Precise High-Speed UV Laser Microstructuring,” *Micromachines* **14**(4), 843 (2023).
32. G. Mincuzzi, A. Rebière, M. Faucon, *et al.*, “Beam engineering strategies for high throughput, precise, micro-cutting by 100 W, femtosecond lasers,” *J. Laser Appl.* **32**(4), 042003 (2020).